

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE PRINCIPLE OF NON-DETERIORATION EMPLOYEE'S POSITION.

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ABSTRACT

The paper explores the labour law principle of non-deterioration of employee's position. It highlights employment contracts, collective agreements, and local regulatory acts must not include provisions that diminish workers' rights and guarantees compared to those provided by legislation. The study analyzes Article 8 of the Labor Code, which affirms the primacy of legal norms with greater force and prohibits the application of any clause that worsens the worker's situation. In research paper the conclusion of individual and collective agreement without worsening the status of worker is emphasized.

The principle of non-deterioration of employee's position is a legal guarantee prohibiting the establishment of conditions in employment contracts and collective agreements that reduce the level of rights and guarantees of workers in comparison with current legislation¹. It is of particular importance in the context of protecting the socio-economic rights of workers and ensuring a fair balance of interests of the parties to labor relations.

In Art. 8 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is stated that any regulatory legal act should not worsen the employee's position in comparison with a regulatory legal act that has greater legal force. No local act, individual legal act of the employer can worsen the employee's position in comparison with regulatory legal acts.

As Lushnikov wrote, in this norm of the article the principle of hierarchy of normative sources of labor law and the relationship between collective agreements and individual labor contracts are applied². If the normative legal act worsens the level of labor rights and guarantees of employees established by the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan or laws, then the Code or the law shall apply. A local regulatory act that worsens the employee's position in comparison with that established by labor legislation, or other regulatory acts, a collective agreement, or agreements shall not be applied. A similar rule applies to the terms of collective agreements and agreements.

Scholars of Tashkent State University of Law defined, contractual regulatory documents (including local regulatory documents) developed and adopted by enterprises and organizations may not contradict the Labor Code, worsen the conditions of employees beyond

¹ Менгураева Н. (2025). Применение Принципа Недопустимости Ухудшения Правового Положения Работника В Трудовых Договорах И Коллективных Соглашениях. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 4(13), 60–62. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zdif/article/view/101839>

² Лушникова, М. В., & Лушников, А. М. (2014). Основные принципы трудового права: актуальные проблемы легализации. *Вестник трудового права и права социального обеспечения*, (8), 84.

those provided for in the Code, or reduce the level of guarantees³. Terms of labor agreements and contracts that worsen the situation of employees beyond what is provided for in labor laws and other regulatory documents are invalid.

The principle of freedom of labour allows parties to conclude individual labour contract based to their free consent and choice. However, the principle of inadmissibility of worsening the employee's position prohibits to add circumstances that can worsen the employee position. The terms of an employment contract that worsen the employee's situation in relation to the legislation, collective agreement, regulations on remuneration and other local regulatory acts shall be considered invalid. It should be mentioned, that only paragraph containing worsening the employee's situation would be invalid, not labour contract at all.

According to Article 104 of the Labor Code, an employment contract may provide for additional conditions, but they must not worsen the employee's position. When concluding an employment contract, the parties do not have the right to include conditions that worsen the employee's position compared to the legislation. The contractual method assumes equality of subjects in developing the terms of the contract, however, in this case the principle of non-deterioration of the position of workers also applies, prohibiting violation of legal rights and interests of employee. In addition, the expression of will of such a party as the employer is largely limited by the agreements existing within the framework of local acts.

Inoyatov provides the following terms may not be established when concluding an employment contract:

- additional grounds for termination of the employment contract, except permitted by law;
- establishing disciplinary sanctions not provided for by law;
- establishing a probationary period exceeding the maximum period established by the Labor Code;
- introducing additional restrictions on part-time work;
- establishing a working time period exceeding that provided for by law;
- introducing financial liability for employees in cases not provided for by law⁴.

Author would bring additional terms, which are considered as deteriorating employee's position. 1) Waiver of statutory guarantees and compensations (paid leave, sick leave, maternity benefits, etc.) 2) Establishing a lower wage than provided by law. 3) no benefits for hazardous working conditions, overtime work, night shifts. 4) Restriction of the right to join trade unions or participate in collective bargaining. 5) Violation of the principle of prohibition forced labour.

The principle of priority of more favorable conditions is manifested in the fact that collective agreements of different levels (general, sectoral, territorial) should not contradict each other in terms of worsening the position of workers⁵. Article 86 of the Labor Code directly indicates that the terms of collective agreements that worsen the position of workers in comparison with collective agreements of a higher level are invalid.

In conclusion, this principle serves as a guarantee prohibiting the establishment of terms in employment contracts and collective agreements that reduce the level of rights and guarantees of workers in comparison with legislation.

³ Муаллифлар жамоаси. Меҳнат ҳуқуқи. Дарслик. –Т.: ТДЮУ нашриёти, 2018. –21 р.

⁴ А.А. Иноятв. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг меҳнат ҳуқуқи. Дарслик – «Иктисодиёт ва ҳуқуқ дунёси», 2002. 130 page.

⁵ Менгтураева Н. (2025). Применение Принципа Недопустимости Ухудшения Правового Положения Работника В Трудовых Договорах И Коллективных Соглашениях. Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования, 4(13), 60–62. извлечено от <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zdif/article/view/101839>

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